

Science

**ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS
DIARRHEAL DISEASES IN CHILDREN UNDER FIVE YEARS IN
SHENDI TOWN**

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ABSTRACT

Diarrheal diseases are a collection of diseases caused by multiple viral, bacterial, and parasitic organisms that share common symptoms, and it's defined as the passage of three or more loose or liquid stool per day. This Descriptive community based cross sectional study was conducted in Shendi Town during the year 2015 to study Knowledge and Attitude towards diarrheal disease in children under five years. A system of simple random sampling allocation was followed to select the sample for coverage of diarrhea disease in Shendi town.

The data was collected through instructed questionnaire according to SNAP standard Questionnaire which contains 20 closed ended questions with simple language that was been easily to understood by the respondents . The collected data was analyzed by entering it into computer and analyzed using both Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences Program (spss). The results then presented in tables and figures, and then subjected to additional statistical analyses T test to find associations and statistical significance by finding P value.

The most important conclusions revealed from the study is, Most of mothers (55%) seek medical treatment when their children got diarrhea. The most important recommendations emerged from this study, Government and Shendi local authorities must educate mothers on diarrheal disease prevention and rehydration, Sufficient programs and facilities should be made available for family planning, Give oriented task health education to health workers.

Keywords:

Diarrheal diseases, children under five years, medical treatment, diarrhea.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Diarrhea: is a familiar phenomenon with unusually frequent or unusually liquid bowel movements, excessive watery evacuations of fecal material, the opposite of constipation. The word "diarrhea" with its odd spelling is a near steal from the Greek "diarrhea" meaning "a flowing through" (www.medicinenet.com, 2012). Diarrhea is the passage of loose or watery stools occurring three or more times in a 24-hour period (Abrams, Benenson, 1995). Diarrhea means an increased frequency or decreased consistency of bowel movements (www.Thefreedictionary.com, 2012). Diarrhea an increase in the fluidity, volume and frequency of stool relative the usual habits of each individual (Concise of American laboratory book, 2011)

Problem Statement: The diarrhea is a very serious disease that causes many cases of diarrhea disease special in children less than 5years and also mortality in Shendi town. And it is the second most common cause of death in young children, after pneumonia. In Shendi town the number of cases of diarrhea in children under five year was 12966 (48%) in last year. And this magnitude problem of diarrhea towards children under 5years old was the reason that guided me to select this topic to study the knowledge attitude and practice towards the mothers about the diarrhea disease in their children.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

This observational community based cross sectional study was conducted in Shendi town, the capital of Shendi locality, River Nile State at north of Sudan. A system of simple random sampling allocation was followed to select the sample *for* coverage of diarrhea disease in Shendi town.

The data was collected through instructed questionnaire according to SNAP standard Questionnaire and contains 20 closed ended questions and a simple language that was been easily to understood by the respondents for starting the easier questions.

The collected data was analyzed by entering it into computer and analyzed using both Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences Program (spss).

The results then presented in tables and figures, and then subjected to additional statistical analyses T test to find associations and statistical significance by finding P value. Data was analyzed using computer, both Microsoft Excel and Statistic Package for Social Sciences program (SPSS), and the results were presented by percentage tables, cross tables and other statistical test of the significance between different factors were examined.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Shows Educational level of households having children under five years in shendi town

<i>Educational level of household</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Ratio</i>
<i>Illiterate</i>	<i>24</i>	<i>20%</i>
<i>Primary</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>10%</i>
<i>Secondary</i>	<i>34</i>	<i>28%</i>

University	38	32%
Post graduate	12	10%
Total	120	100%

Figure 1: Shows the number of children below five years in Shendi town

Figure 2: Shows the awareness about causes of diarrhea according to shendi town households

Figure 3: Shows the household concept regarding the best treatment of diarrhea among children

4. DISCUSSION

The study demonstrated that an education level of shendi population varied from illiteracy to postgraduate (table -1) with significant number of primary school educated mother this situation in addition to other factors such as having more than two under five children in more families (figure -1) contribute to adopting bad attitudes and worse habits and practices towards diarrheal disease.

Also the study showed that most mother took their children to hospital when causes diarrheal disease in staid of taking traditional treatment material (figure-3), thus reveals the higher leavens on medical services although only (18%) of them gives their children O.R.s.

But there are other factors related such as availability of medical services distributed by ministry of health and shendi university hospitals and health centers, family size and educational variations. These factors must be taken into account, as they may strongly influence mothers and community's awareness and attitudes towards diarrheal diseases programs.

The study finds that most population thought that causes of their children by diarrhea due to using unclean (dirty) bottle (figure -2), so this can be avoided by a applied strong sanitation program by local health authorities.

5. CONCLUSION

In Shendi city, the number of diarrheal cases is high among the children under five years, and this can only be reduced by changing the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Mothers towards the disease, and it can be achieved through the interventional programs (Control and Prevention).

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Local health authority should Educating mothers to increase the number of breast feeds, because of its benefits for both the mother and the child.
- Local health authority should Increasing the effectiveness of diarrheal disease control programs, Especially flies control in summer season,
- Give intensive oriented task health education among health workers, communities, and households
- Developing a two-to-five year plan to reduce diarrhoea mortality.
- Evaluating progress by monitoring usage rates of oral rehydration therapy (ORT)/ORS, home-based treatment, and zinc supplementation.
- Improving the Environmental Sanitation status.
- Motivate or encouraging mothers to participate the control of diarrhea.

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8. REFERENCES

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